

Chocolate Babies Melting Due to Maltreatment

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B.Manjula, M.A, DBPO, DIY,DCE, MA (Linguistics),,

Assistant Professor of English, ARC Visvanathan College

Railway Junction, Mayiladuthurai

Abstract

The terms child abuse and child maltreatment is physical, sexual, and or psychological maltreatment or neglect of a child or children, especially by a parent or other caregiver, child abuse may include any act or failure to act by a parent other caregiver that results in actual or potential harm to a child, and can occur in a child’s home or in the organizations, schools or communities the child interacts with all mass media.

The terms child abuse and child maltreatment are often interchangeably, although some researchers make a distinction between them, treating child maltreatment as an umbrella term to cover neglect, exploitation and trafficking.

Different jurisdictions have developed their own definitions of what constitutes child abuse for the purpose of removing children from their families or prosecuting a criminal charge.

Child Abuse

Most children who come to the attention of the child welfare system do so because of any of the following situations, which are often collectively termed child abuse. Abuse typically involves abuse of power, or exercising power for an unintended purpose. This includes willful neglect, knowingly not exercising a power for the purpose it was intended. This is why child abuse is defined as taking advantage of a position of trust having been invested with powers.

Physical Abuse

Physical abuse is physical assault or battery on the child. Whilst an assault has some adverse consequence that the victim did not agree to (the difference between surgery and stabbing) the victim agrees to the consequences of battery but the agreement is fraudulent in some way (e.g. unnecessary surgery under false pretences). Physical abuse also harassment, a physical presence intended to provoke fear.

Child Sexual Abuse

Child sexual abuse is sexual assault or battery on the child. The vast majority of physical assaults are a reaction to a situation involving a specific victim. Sexual assault is predominantly perpetrator gratification against any suitable target. Sexual abuse covers the range of direct and indirect assaults (e.g. imagery) and the means of facilitation such as stalking and internet offences.

- Neglect, including failure to take adequate measures to safeguard a child from harm, and gross negligence in providing for a child’s basic needs. Needs are the actions to be taken to protect and provide for the child. Safeguarding is the duty of a person given the powers of responsibility for the child to take the necessary measures to protect the child. If a child is physically or sexually abused then there is an (abusive) person responsible for the assault and a (negligent) person responsible for failing to protect from the assault. In some cases they may be the same.
- Psychological abuse, when meeting the child’s needs by taking the necessary steps to protect and provide for the child the child’s wishes and feelings must be considered when deciding on delivery of the provision that best serves the child’s needs. Wilfully failing to provide by the child’s wishes and feelings, while it is in his/her best interests is emotional abuse (intentional infliction of emotional distress) or negligently is emotional neglect (negligent infliction of emotional distress).

Parental Responsibility

In 1984 the Council of Europe, the body that supervises the European Convention on Human Rights, make Recommendation Parental Responsibilities. These defined parental responsibility as a ‘function’ duties to be met and powers that can be exercised to meet those duties. Child abuse and neglect is failure by a person with parental or any other protective responsibility to exercise the powers for the intended purpose, which is the benefit of the child.

Actions typically include services aimed at supporting at-risk families so they can remain intact to safeguard and promote the welfare of the child, investigation of alleged child abuse and, if necessary, assuming parental responsibility by foster care and adoption services.

Child Protection

Most countries have introduced laws to protect and prevent children and young persons from certain threats or harms.

United Kingdom

In 1908 the Children Act 1908 was introduced followed by the Children and Young Person Act 1920 with a bundle of laws to protect young persons and children in the early 20th century. The Children and Young Persons Act 1933 consolidated the laws into a single law.

The Children Act 1933 defined child neglect and abuse as is now currently understood[6] in the context of welfare and well-being. Welfare (health, safety and happiness) is the ‘fare’, nourishment, that makes a person ‘well’, healthy.

One commentator notes that ‘the period before 1948 saw the majority of work with vulnerable children undertaken by ‘moral’ or family welfare workers. These were mostly voluntary workers based within groups such as the Church of England’s Moral Welfare Associations. Their remit also included supporting ‘friendless girls’, unmarried mothers and babies, intervening to prevent prostitution, and helping treat and prevent the spread of venereal disease. Boys were not widely perceived as sexually vulnerable, and barely featured in discussions of child assault and prostitution.’[7]

Well-being is the personal motivation and aspiration for security, comfort and emotional contentment that drives the process. The offence of child cruelty under section 1 of the Children and Young Peoples Act 1989 protects health and safety. Learning, as the other essential ingredient to the pursuit of well-being, is covered by section 44.

Child protection and the prevention of neglect and abuse follows this model throughout. This was the approach that led the policy imperative for eradicating child poverty in a system of public health epidemiology. A programme international promoted by the World Health Organisation in the Health For All programming goal and nationally as Health for All Children. The public health imperative of well-being is exactly mirrored in the socio-economic philosophy of capabilities as welfare economics.

While the Children and Young People Act 1933 established the foundations they were later consolidated into the state’s employment, education, health and welfare by the Children Act 1989 and following tranche of legislation. Internationally, the principles were embodied in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.

Important Changes in 1933

- Minimum age of execution was raised from 16 to 18 years.
- The age of criminal responsibility was raised from 7 to 8 years.
- Introduction of a minimum working age of 14 years.
- The minimum age to smoke and to buy tobacco products was set at 16 years.
- The minimum age for prostitution and to enter a brothel is set at 16 years.
- The minimum age to give alcohol to a child on private premises is set at 5 years.
- Safeguarding the welfare of the child edit
- Child safeguarding follows directly from these principles. Safeguarding means taking the necessary protective measures for the child’s safe consumption of any product, stair-gates, seatbelts, protective footwear, glasses, basic hygiene, etc. The list is both endless and, to the most part, obvious common sense. Failure by the responsible person is an offence of child cruelty on the grounds of failing to protect the child in circumstances consistent with the provision of safe and effective care.[8][9]
- A parent, person with parental responsibility for a child, has an express liability, whoever is responsible for the child at the time (s.17 of the act). Just as in employment health and safety, the powers of parenthood can be delegated but not the duties. Parents should make arrangements for suitable and properly informed others to have responsibility for their children (see also s.2(9)-(11) Children Act 1989).
- The best interests of the child edit
- Decision making edits
- Decisions made on all the necessary products: environments, accommodation, goods and services procured to be provided for the child’s safe consumption must be in the best interests of the child. A child is a person, not an object of concern who simply lacks the capacity to give consent on her own behalf until Gillick Competent to do so. He/she must still be involved in the decision making processes for the products that best serve his/her needs by the best interests determination of s.4 Mental Capacity Act 2005. Failure of the responsible person to do so is an offence on the grounds of emotional neglect (see, Part 2 B, 24, sentencing guidance, Overarching Principles: Overarching Principles: Assaults on children Assaults on children and Cruelty to a child; and Introduction, Working Together to Safeguard Children (HMG 2015) the governmental child protection guidance).

Disability, Parental Disability and Social Inclusion

The Department of Work and Pensions disability assessment is a measure of physical and mental capacities under clinical or controlled conditions from occupational health in respect to employment performance. The test for disability is capability as “the mental or physical impairment with an adverse effect on day-to-day activities” as social performance. The assessment of capacity is used in a home-based disability assessment under s.47 NHS and Community Care Act 1990.

- For a parent, a parental disability is a mental or physical impairment with the adverse effect on the day-to-day activity of giving the child the care it would be reasonable to expect a parent to give a similar child (s.31 Children Act 1989)
- Whatever their mental or physical impairments parents should be given the necessary disability support to care for their children to maintain a reasonable standard of health and development. (s.17(10) Children Act 1989).[
- For those with parental responsibility mental capacity to make decisions in own best interests is extended to parental capacity to make decisions in the best interests of the child by Working Together to Safeguard Children. The s.47 disability assessment is extended by Part III and s.8 Part 1 Schedule 2 Children Act 1989.
- Part III Children Act 1989 includes s.17 and the local authority duty to safeguard and promote the welfare of children by the provision of services for the families of children in need. The services include advocacy services for advice and assistance in decision making when exercising the authorities of parental responsibility. This was another clear intention of the act described in the Department of Health Introduction as “...the belief that children are best brought up in the family with both parents playing a full part...the local authority duty to provide support for children and families...”

Web Sources

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